

MARKOV CHAIN ANALYSIS FOR NATURAL DISASTER PREDICTION OF PALM OIL INDUSTRY SUPPLY CHAIN AT JAMBI PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

Every year, natural disasters cause damage and losses. In this context, disaster prediction needs to be proposed to address disasters and emergencies by improving disaster prediction during disaster response. Therefore, collecting historical data activity will assist in classifying disasters and predicting future disaster events. Natural disaster Prediction and response systems require to predict natural disasters. Markov analysis is applied the analytical technique in this research, which is frequently used in the palm oil industry for Supply Chain operation. The research contribution presents the context of natural disaster prediction, which relates to palm oil agro-industry supply chain management. It is connected to predicting future disaster events by applying Markov chain analysis for Natural Disaster Prediction in Jambi Province. The aim is to minimize the impact of disasters on the oil palm supply chain.

Keywords: Mrkov Chain; Natural Disaster; Prediction; Supply Chain

GEL classifications:

INTRODUCTION

Natural disasters are unexpected events that affect countries worldwide. The same is true in Indonesia, where floods, landslides, floods and landslides, abrasion, tornadoes, droughts, forest and land fires, earthquakes, tsunamis, earthquakes, and tsunamis, and volcanic eruptions cause considerable damage, monetary costs, mass evacuation, distress, injury, and deaths. For example, the Tsunami disaster that occurred in Aceh Province occurred on December 26, 2004. The tsunami was produced by a magnitude 9.3 earthquake that struck 30 kilometers beneath the seabed and was centered around 100 kilometers off the province's west coast, Aceh. More than 220,000 people died in Indonesia as a result of the disaster. The earthquake and tsunami in Aceh were the most devastating natural catastrophes in Indonesian history, with the highest number of victims [1]. Another incident was the earthquake in Lombok, where a series of earthquakes was first felt from 29 July to 19 August 2018, with a magnitude of 5.9-6.9. Since then, there has been a series of aftershocks on a small to large scale, accounting for hundreds of times. This disaster caused a recorded death toll of 553 people [2][3][4]. The latest disaster was the earthquake and tsunami in Palu and Donggala, which caused severe damage to Palu and Donggala Regency in, Central Sulawesi. On Friday

afternoon, September 28, 2018, a magnitude 7.4 earthquake was followed by a tsunami that ruined hundreds of buildings and took thousands of lives; at least 1,407 people died as a victim of the disaster[5].

The high risk of being affected by disasters in Indonesia makes us always ready to take various anticipatory actions by utilizing advances in technology and mathematical models to predict and minimize the occurrence and impact of natural disasters. Jambi is a province on the island of Sumatra, an area that is geographically, climatologically, and demographically located in a disaster-prone area. It can be seen from the Jambi Province disaster data that there are types of disaster events, including flood, landslide, flood and landslide, abrasion, tornado, droughts, forest, apeople'sd fires, earthquake, tsunami, earthquake and tsunami, and volcano eruption[6]. Jambi Province is also one of the areas where the intensity of natural disasters also often occurs.

Figure 1 Description of the disaster condition map of Jambi Province (Source: petabencana.id/map/Jambi)

In addition, to predict disaster events in the future based on historical data on disaster events, stakeholders can use them to mitigate and make decisions on disaster management to anticipate and reduce the impact of disasters caused. Without proper warning and mitigation, disaster events will have a bigger influence on losses. It is a problem that needs to be anticipated; one way is by making predictions so that we can expect and can take better countermeasures. Based on this, a formula or prediction pattern is needed as new knowledge to reduce the impact of disaster events or as input so that stakeholders can mitigate natural disasters early [7]. Following a succession of disasters, it is critical to establish a solid mitigation system [8].

This paper proposes a model for prediction and mitigation and a disaster response system for natural disaster events in Jambi Province. Regional Disaster Management Agency (BPBD) of

data, especially for the Jambi Province Region on its official website, shows a significant change from the number of disasters that existed in 2016 to 2020. The existing data shows that the incidence of disasters tends to continue to increase. For this reason, it is necessary to predict the occurrence of natural disasters in Jambi Province by utilizing historical data and conducting analysis to predict future disaster events; the data used is data mining techniques with the Markov Chains algorithm. The state of a system shifting from one to another is referred to as a Markov process[9]. Markov Chains is an algorithm that calculates based on the probability value of the occurrence of the previous event through the estimated value of the observed transition. A Markov chain can be thought of as a series of possibility state transitions. A stochastic process where the probability of a future state transition was original look by the current state [10]. In terms of intelligent transportation, user location prediction in location-based social networks can accurately anticipate the density of people movement [11]. According to the historical data of disaster events, the Markov chains algorithm is compatible with the concept of probability. The historical occurrence of existing disasters is compared based on the value of the matrix to predict natural disasters in the coming year in percentage value. Thus, the expected value generated will provide input to related parties in disaster management strategies earlier. Prediction theory can be used to examine both natural and social phenomena as a broad methodology. The Markov process is a type of stochastic process that is studied in current probability theory. It's been widely employed and has a significant impact on a variety of domains, including communication, control, biology, social science, and other scientific and technological fields[12]. In practice, people regularly come with a random process that has the following characteristics: when its current state is known, its future evolution is independent of its previous evolution. The random process with this quality is termed Markov process [13]. The independent characteristic of "future" and "past" under the constraint of known "present" is called Markov process. By studying the evolution trend and state of a Markov chain, Markov analysis is a method for predicting the future state of things [14].

The proposed model relies on the following four main categories: (i) retrieval of historical disaster data, ii) data processing for disaster identification and prediction, (iii) disaster event analysis, and (iv) application of disaster data into algorithms to obtain analysis results. The main contributions of this paper are threefold:

- Mathematical models for assessing and predicting disasters;
- Analysis of the calculation of the value of disaster predictions;
- Design of systems for predicting disasters;

In the discussion, this paper will be explained as follows. The first part discusses the introduction, the second part discusses the research method. The third section shows the findings and discussion. Finally, Section IV contains the conclusions and recommendations for our subsequent works.

1. Research Method

This research provides a data collecting system paradigm for detecting and predicting natural disasters. The system model offered, as depicted in Figure 2, is divided into 4 parts, namely:

- Historical data collection for disaster-related data acquisition
- Data processing for analysis
- Algorithm application and analysis
- Results of analysis and prediction of disasters that occurred during a certain period

Figure2. Concept and System Model Analysis and Prediction

Figure2. Concept and System Model Analysis and Prediction describes proposed system model components for disaster prediction and detection related to data processing that will be carried out for analysis, algorithm application and data processing results, and prediction of natural disasters in Jambi Province as follows:

a. Data collection

The research data comes from disaster event reports on the BPBD website recorded from 2016 to 2020, including data on the number of disaster events every year and month and based on the type of disaster event.

b. Defining a Data Set

Data Seeing from complex data where in one year there are various kinds of events, the calculation is carried out by calculating the number of possibilities for each disaster in each year and month. Data from 2016 to 2020. Then the formulation is carried out using the Markov chain algorithm.

c. Perform data analysis with Markov Chain Algorithm

The data is formed into a matrix and then calculated using the Markov chain formula. The value obtained is in the form of the value of each disaster event in Jambi Province.

d. Evaluation and validation

This evaluation and validation stage evaluates the prediction results with the existing analytical data.

The research flow above is described process flow diagram form as shown in Figure 3.

Figure3. The study steps conceptual modeling of prediction natural disaster for supply chain management

A. Data Collection

The BNPB disaster data from 2016 to 2020 was used to collect disaster prediction and detection data.. In this system, the approach that emerges is data acquisition from public data sources on the [https://dibi page.bnpb.go.id/](https://dibi.page.bnpb.go.id/). This method examines comprehensive data

collected in real-time from ongoing disasters and emergencies [15], i.e., how disasters and emergencies change over time for decision-making; disaster data will be monitored and analyzed. Table 1 shows the data sources for data collecting. The graph depicts the different sorts of catastrophes in Jambi Province from 2016 to 2020, based on BPBD records available on their official website [https://dibi page.bnpb.go.id/](https://dibi.page.bnpb.go.id/)

Table1. Jambi Province Natural Disaster Data in 2016-2020

Period	Flood	Landslide	Tornado	Forest and Land Fires
January 2016	4	3	0	0
February 2016	5	0	1	0
March 2016	3	0	0	0
April 2016	5	0	0	0
May 2016	2	0	0	0
June 2016	0	0	0	0
July 2016	0	0	1	0
August 2016	0	0	1	1
September 2016	0	0	0	0
October 2016	1	1	1	0
November 2016	1	1	0	0
December 2016	3	0	2	0
January 2017	1	2	1	0
February 2017	3	1	0	0
March 2017	3	0	0	0
April 2017	0	0	1	0
May 2017	5	0	0	0
June 2017	3	0	0	0
July 2017	0	0	0	1
August 2017	1	0	2	1
September 2017	0	0	0	0
October 2017	0	0	1	0
November 2017	1	0	1	0
December 2017	1	0	0	0
January 2018	0	0	0	0
February 2018	0	0	0	0
March 2018	1	1	0	0
April 2018	1	1	1	0
May 2018	1	0	0	2
June 2018	0	0	1	4
July 2018	0	0	0	4
August 2018	0	0	0	1
September 2018	0	1	2	0
October 2018	0	0	0	0
November 2018	2	1	1	0

December 2018	2	0	1	0
January 2019	0	0	0	0
February 2019	4	0	1	0
March 2019	2	0	1	0
April 2019	3	0	1	0
May 2019	2	0	0	0
June 2019	0	1	0	1
July 2019	0	0	0	5
August 2019	0	0	0	1
September 2019	0	0	1	3
October 2019	0	0	0	0
November 2019	0	0	0	0
December 2019	1	1	0	0
January 2020	2	0	1	0
February 2020	3	0	0	1
March 2020	2	0	0	1
April 2020	5	0	0	0
May 2020	6	0	0	0
June 2020	2	0	0	12
July 2020	1	0	0	4
August 2020	0	0	2	17
September 2020	1	0	0	8
October 2020	3	0	3	14
November 2020	11	1	1	0
December 2020	3	0	0	0

Floods (F), Landslide (L), Tornado (T), Forest and Land Fires (FLF)

From the data above, it can be seen that the number of disasters that occur every year with several types of disasters, namely Flood (F), Forest and Land Fires (FLF), Tornado (T), and Landslides (L) in Jambi Province.

B. Perform data analysis with Markov Chains Algorithm

Our proposed data processing component is used to analyze and predict future disaster events. Data collection will represent the main data source as a component of the system model processing that will be used as a data source for analysis. Next, the algorithm will be applied to analyze disaster predictions. The algorithm will be used in the future to determine the probability of natural disasters. Based on data from historical disaster events from 2016 to 2020 will be used to train the algorithm. The historical data collected will be used to predict the occurrence of disasters at an early stage, then used to evaluate and predict disaster events.

Natural disaster prediction is made by utilizing data mining methods. In this paper, the Markov Chains algorithm is used to calculate the probability value of the event against the previous historical event through the estimation of the observed transition value[10]. The Markov chains algorithm follows the concept of probability based on historical disaster data to predict natural disasters in the coming year as a disaster management strategy to reduce the

impact of losses. Mathematically Markov Chain Algorithm can be written:

$$Kt(j) = P \times Kt(j - 1) \quad (1)$$

Kt (j) = Probability Level of occurrence on
t (j)

P = Transitional Probability Value

t (j) = Time to-j

The probability of occurrence of Kt (j) is represented in vector form so that the sum of all cells is always 100%.

Absolute Probability and Transition Values

The general expression of {aj0} in the form of {aj0} and P can be written as follows.

$$a_{j(1)} = a_{1(0)} + P_{1j} + a_{2(0)} P_{2j} + \dots = \sum a_i^{(0)} P_{ij} \quad (2)$$

Next

$$a_{j(2)} = \sum_i a_{i(1)} P_{ij} = \sum_i (\sum_k a_{k(0)} P_{ki}) P_{ij} = \sum_k a_{k(0)} (\sum_i P_{ki} P_{ij}) = \sum_k a_{k(0)} P_{kj}^{(2)} \quad (3)$$

Two-step or second-order transition probability), that is, the potential of moving from state k to state j in exactly two transitions. Similarly, it can be shown by induction that:

$$a_{j(n)} = \sum_i a_{i(0)} (\sum_k P_{ik}^{(n-1)} P_{kj} \sum_i a_{i(0)} P_{ij}^{(n)}) \quad (4)$$

where $P_{ij}^{(n)}$ is the transition probability n steps or order n by recursive formula.

$$P_{ij}^{(n)} = \sum_i P_{ik}^{(n-1)} P_{kj} \quad (5)$$

In general, for all i and j

$$P_{ij}^{(n)} = \sum_k P_{ik}^{(n-m)} P_{kj}^{(m)}, 0 < m < n \quad (6)$$

These equations are known as the Chapman-Kolmogorov equations. Higher transition elements and matrices $\|P_{ij}(n)\|$ can be obtained directly by matrix multiplication.

$$\|P_{ij(2)}\| = \|P_{ij}\| \|P_{ij}\| = P^2$$

$$\|P_{ij(3)}\| = \|P_{ij}^2\| \|P_{ij}\| = P^3$$

Figure5. Landslide data graph

Figure6. Tornado data graph

Figure7. Forest and land fires data graph

The number of floods, landslides, cyclones, and forest and land fires from 2016 to 2020 can be seen in the graph as shown in Figures 4 to 7. It is known that floods in 2016 occurred from January-May 2016 and October to December. From 2016 - to 2017, floods occurred from January to March, May, June, August, November, and December, then in 2018, floods occurred from March to May, and November, December 2018. In 2019 floods occurred from February to April and December. In 2020, floods occurred from January to December except for August. Landslides in 2016 occurred in January, October, and November. In 2017, there were no landslides; in 2018, they appeared in March, April, September, and November. In 2019, landslides only occurred in June and December. In 2020 there were almost no landslides except in November. Tornado events occurred in February, July, August, October, and December 2016. In 2017 they appeared in January, April, August, October, and November. 2018 occurs in April, June, September, November, and December. The year 2019 occurs in February, March, April, and September. While in 2020, January, August, October, and November. Furthermore, land and forest fires occurred in August 2016, July and August 2017, and from May to August 2018. In 2019 it occurred from June to September, and in 2020 it happens in February and March, from June to October.

B. Transition State

The Markov analysis approach is a dynamic stochastic mathematical model based on system "state" and "state transition" ideas [16]. In the transition state section, data on natural disasters in the form of floods, landslides, tornadoes, as well as forest and land fires that occurred from 2016 to 2020 will be analyzed to identify the probability level of future disasters. The data is categorized into historical data every year, to be further identified every month whether a disaster occurs or not as shown in Table 2.

Table2. Transition State

Month	Flood	State	Landslide	State	Tornado	State	Forest and Land Fires	State
January 2016	4	Yes	3	Yes	0	No	0	No
February 2016	5	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
March 2016	3	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
April 2016	5	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
May 2016	2	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
June 2016	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
July 2016	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
August 2016	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	1	Yes
September 2016	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
October 2016	1	Yes	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No
November 2016	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No	0	No
December 2016	3	Yes	0	No	2	Yes	0	No
January 2017	1	Yes	2	Yes	1	Yes	0	No
February 2017	3	Yes	1	Yes	0	No	0	No
March 2017	3	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
April 2017	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
May 2017	5	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
June 2017	3	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
July 2017	0	No	0	No	0	No	1	Yes
August 2017	1	Yes	0	No	2	Yes	1	Yes
September 2017	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
October 2017	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
November 2017	1	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
December 2017	1	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
January 2018	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
February 2018	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
March 2018	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No	0	No
April 2018	1	Yes	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No
May 2018	1	Yes	0	No	0	No	2	Yes
June 2018	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	4	Yes
July 2018	0	No	0	No	0	No	4	Yes
August 2018	0	No	0	No	0	No	1	Yes
September 2018	0	No	1	Yes	2	Yes	0	No
October 2018	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
November 2018	2	Yes	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No
December 2018	2	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
January 2019	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
February 2019	4	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
March 2019	2	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
April 2019	3	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
May 2019	2	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No

June 2019	0	No	1	Yes	0	No	1	Yes
July 2019	0	No	0	No	0	No	5	Yes
August 2019	0	No	0	No	0	No	1	Yes
September 2019	0	No	0	No	1	Yes	3	Yes
October 2019	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
November 2019	0	No	0	No	0	No	0	No
December 2019	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No	0	No
January 2020	2	Yes	0	No	1	Yes	0	No
February 2020	3	Yes	0	No	0	No	1	Yes
March 2020	2	Yes	0	No	0	No	1	Yes
April 2020	5	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
May 2020	6	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No
June 2020	2	Yes	0	No	0	No	12	Yes
July 2020	1	Yes	0	No	0	No	4	Yes
August 2020	0	No	0	No	2	Yes	17	Yes
September 2020	1	Yes	0	No	0	No	8	Yes
October 2020	3	Yes	0	No	3	Yes	14	Yes
November 2020	11	Yes	1	Yes	1	Yes	0	No
December 2020	3	Yes	0	No	0	No	0	No

Floods (F), Landslide (L), Tornado (T), Forest and Land Fires (FLF)

C. Transition Probability Matrix

Based on the data shown in Table 2, it can be seen that the data used is historical data on the time span of disaster events in 2016-2020 which occurs every month. Then the researcher determines the status of the occurrence and non-occurrence of disasters which are presented in the following matrix:

Table3. Transition Period of Flood (F)

Status	Position of Transition		Sum
	Yes	No	
Yes	27	9	36
No	9	14	23
Sum	36	23	59

In the data in the transition table of each type of disaster can be seen the sum of each state and the change in position of the transition. The change value corresponds to the current state with the next state. So that obtained for the type of flood disaster, the current value of a disaster occurs then the next transition occurs disaster back to 27, the current value of the disaster occurred while the next did not amount to 9, and the current value of no disaster occurred, the next value of the disaster occurred was 9, and the value of now did not occur and the next disaster did not occur amounted to 14.

Table4. Transition Period of Landslide (L)

Status	Position of Transition		Sum
	Yes	No	
Yes	3	9	12
No	8	39	47
Sum	11	48	59

The next disaster event is a landslide, the current value of the disaster occurred then the next transition occurred the disaster again was 3, the current value of the disaster occurred while the next did not amount to 9, and the current value of no disaster occurred, the next value of the disaster occurred was 8, and the value of now not happening and the next disaster did not occur totaling 39.

Table5. Transition Period of Tornado (T)

Status	Position of Transition		Sum
	Yes	No	
Yes	7	16	23
No	16	20	36
Sum	23	36	59

As for the type of tornado disaster, the current value of the disaster occurred and then the next transition occurred disaster back to 7, the current value of the disaster occurred while the next did not amount to 16, and the current value of no disaster occurred, the next value of the disaster occurred was 16, and the current value did not occur and the next disaster did not occur amounted to 20.

Table6. Transition Period of Forest and Land Fires (FLF)

Status	Position of Transition		Sum
	Yes	No	
Yes	12	6	18
No	6	35	41
Sum	18	41	59

Then for forest and land fire disasters, the current value of a disaster occurs then the next transition occurs disaster back to 12, the current value of the disaster while the next does not amount to 6, and the current value of no disaster, the next value of the disaster occurs is 6, and the value of now not happening and the next no disaster is 35. So that the overall total is the same, both floods, landslides, tornadoes and forest and land fires 59.

A transition probability matrix is a matrix that contains information that governs the system's passage from one state to another. The probability that the system is in state I with respect to a state j in earlier observations is given by P in a Markov chain with $X_t, t=0, 1, 2, \dots$ and state

space 0, 1, ..., m. With a matrix size of m x m, the probability of Markov chain transition matrix has positive elements (0) in the P matrix and the number of elements in one row of the transition probability matrix is 1[17].

Thus,

$$P[P_{ij}] = \begin{matrix} \text{Initial State (i)} \\ i_0 \\ i_1 \\ \dots \\ i_s \end{matrix} \begin{matrix} \text{Final State (j)} \\ i_0 & i_1 & \dots & i_s \\ \left[\begin{array}{cccc} P_{0,0} & P_{0,1} & \dots & P_{0,s} \\ P_{1,0} & P_{1,1} & \dots & P_{1,s} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ P_{s,0} & P_{s,1} & \dots & P_{s,s} \end{array} \right] \end{matrix}$$

Where: s is the number of states

The displacement period of each type of disaster from the occurrence of floods, landslides, tornadoes, and forest and land fires is shown in Tables 3 to 6, then, the Transition probability table (P) is crafted from the displacement table. The transition probability P is acquired as shown in the following matrix:

$$P_{\text{Flood}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.75 & 0.25 \\ 0.39 & 0.61 \end{bmatrix}$$

The probability of a catastrophic event occurring or not in the 1st month, and so on is written in a line vector. A value of 0 to declare no disaster occurred, and a value of 1 that states a disaster occurred, so it can be written:

$$\mu_{1\text{flood}} = [0.750000 \quad 0.250000]$$

The probability of a landslide catastrophic event, written in a vector:

$$P_{\text{Landslide}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.25 & 0.75 \\ 0.17 & 0.83 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mu_{1\text{Landslide}} = [0.250000 \quad 0.750000]$$

The probability of a tornado catastrophic event, written in a vector:

$$P_{\text{Tornado}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.30 & 0.70 \\ 0.44 & 0.56 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mu_{1\text{Tornado}} = [0.304348 \quad 0.695652]$$

The probability of catastrophic occurrence of forest and land fires, written in a vector:

$$P_{\text{Forest and Land Fires}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.67 & 0.33 \\ 0.15 & 0.85 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\mu_1_{\text{Forest and Land fires}} = [0.666667 \quad 0.333333]$$

C. Transition Probability Matrix of n-step and Steady State

From the Transition Probability Matrix, which exists in the type of flood disaster, further stages are carried out by multiplying the disaster state with the disaster data matrix, until finding the same or fixed equilibrium point or value, in the type of flood disaster the equilibrium point is in the eighth step with their respective values as follows:

$$P^{(8)}_{\text{Flood}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.61 & 0.39 \\ 0.61 & 0.39 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M_{\text{finalFlood}} = [0.610276 \quad 0.389724]$$

As for the type of landslide disaster, the equilibrium point or the same or fixed value, in the type of landslide disaster the equilibrium point is in the eighth step with the respective values as follows:

$$P^{(8)}_{\text{Landslide}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.18 & 0.82 \\ 0.18 & 0.82 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M_{\text{finalLandslide}} = [0.184971 \quad 0.815029]$$

For the third type of disaster, namely a tornado, an equilibrium point or an equal or fixed value, the equilibrium point is in the fourth step with the respective values as follows:

$$P^{(4)}_{\text{Tornado}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.39 & 0.61 \\ 0.39 & 0.61 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M_{\text{finalTornado}} = [0.390066 \quad 0.609934]$$

Finally, for forest and land fires disaster types, the equilibrium point is at step 16 with each value as follows:

$$P^{(16)}_{\text{Forest and Land Fires}} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.31 & 0.69 \\ 0.31 & 0.69 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$M_{\text{finalTornado}} = [0.305105 \quad 0.694895]$$

The first probability period, P1, determines the probability P2. P1 is divided by P1. Then P2 is multiplied by P2 for P4. When the probability reaches an equilibrium value, the calculation is terminated. The probability value of the four disasters is calculated for each of the following time periods until they reach a steady state, fixed value, or equilibrium: floods and landslides in the eighth period (August 2021), tornadoes in the fourth period (April 2021), and land and forest fires in the sixteenth century (April 2022).

Figure8. Graph Transition Probability Matrix

D. Forecasting Result Evaluation

In Figure 8, the probability comparison occurs the four types of disasters on the y-axis is the presence and absence of natural disasters percentage such as floods, landslides, hurricanes, and land and forest fires. The possibility of flooding is very high compared to the probability of landslides, tornadoes, and land and forest fires, which is 62%. The lowest chance of occurrence of disasters is landslides which are 20%. The analysis results show that during the rainy season, which runs from September to December, floods, landslides, and hurricanes are always present. It also applies to floods that occur more frequently from September to March and landslides that occur more frequently from January to April. Flooding, landslides, and tornadoes can all be predicted ahead of time, which helps to reduce disaster losses.

Figure9. Graph Probability Natural Disaster

E. Disaster prediction for Palm Oil Supply Chain System in Jambi Province

In general, a supply chain can be defined as a group of enterprises that provide products, services, financial services, and information from a source to a client and are directly linked by one or more of the upstream and downstream flows[18]. The supply chain is companies network that collaborate to produce and shipment a product to end-users [19][20]. The supply chain satisfies customers by collaborating to create products and deliver them on time and in good condition. The palm oil supply chain begins with harvesting palm fruit, which is then transmitted to palm oil plantations and palm oil mills. The oil palm supply chain model starts when the palm fresh fruit bunches are harvested; then, through the collectors, the oil palm fruit bunches are sent to intermediaries including traders, farmer groups, and cooperatives for further delivery to the palm oil processing factory. The Oil Palm Supply Chain System in Jambi Province is home to some of Sumatra's most significant oil palm plantations. Oil palm plantations cover 574,514 hectares in Jambi Province. In Jambi Province, there are 33 Palm Oil Mills (PKS) with 26 companies Table 7.

Table 7. Palm Oil Mills (PKS) in Operation in Jambi Province

No.	City	Sum		Production Capacity		
		PKS	Factory	Legal	Standby	Used
11	BBatanghari	3	3	205	205	145
22	Muaro Jambi	10	8	450	450	405
33	BBungo	4	4	225	195	135
44	SSarolangun	1	1	60	60	57
55	Merangin	5	2	300	270	215
66	TTanjab Barat	6	5	350	280	254
77	TTebo	4	3	165	165	150
Sum		33	26	1755	1625	1361

Resource: Jambi Province[21]

The supply chain system in Jambi Province starts with harvesting Oil Palm Fruits. Harvesting activities are carried out, starting with fruit cutting activities. Then the FFB is transported for collection. Transportation is usually done by truck or motorbike. After the fruit is collected, it is transported to the factory using trucks, wheel tractors, and dump trucks. According to Anthony & Govindarajan [22] it is a variable that the company must consider because it identifies the factors that make the business successful and those that hinder it, where the situation requires quick handling. The purpose of identifying success factors is to determine which variables are important and which variables are less important in supporting competitive advantage. Based on this, identifying success factors is very important if you look at the current issue of palm oil sustainability. Identification of success factors will help stakeholders such as farmers, traders, and cooperatives to PKS make decisions to manage sustainability issues properly. The palm oil supply chain system in Jambi Province starts from the plantations of farmers, traders, Gapoktan, and cooperatives, then to palm oil mills. This study focuses on managing the independent smallholder rather than the mill's partnership palm field, which is well-managed. The dealer serves as a link between the independent

farmer and the palm oil mill[23]. As a result, the study's scope was limited to smallholder farmers, traders, and palm oil mills. The mechanism of the oil palm supply chain in Jambi Province is as illustrated in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Supply chain structure in Jambi Province

Based on the description of the palm oil supply chain in Jambi in Figure 4, there are four main supply chain areas in Jambi Province. The four regions include plantations, transportation from gardens to collectors, traders, gapoktan and cooperatives, factories, and transportation from traders, gapoktan, and cooperatives to factories. During the harvesting process, transportation from plantations to traders, Gapoktan or cooperatives to delivery to palm oil mills, information is needed regarding the prediction of obstacles and dangers when supply chain business processes occur. This is to minimize events that can disrupt business processes that occur. For example, transportation from plantations to factories which are part of the palm oil supply chain has an impact on disrupting palm oil supply chain activities caused by delays in delivery due to disasters. Therefore, disaster mitigation is a success factor for transportation. If there are obstacles, then the delivery of goods will experience delays due to a truck breaking down or the vehicle's speed that cannot be increased.

Risk reduction in the palm oil supply chain in Indonesia is mainly accomplished by improving coordination between the three components of the palm oil supply chain, namely plantations, port production, and storage[24]. The most common technique to assure the efficacy of such coordination utilizing the framework is to constantly predict risks and assess supply chain performance, allowing for more effective and efficient planning and control of the palm oil supply chain[25]. This research provides a conceptual framework for managing a sustainable palm oil supply chain that incorporates catastrophe prediction into the palm oil supply chain's planning and control. Disaster prediction is also needed to maintain the sustainability of fresh fruit bunches supply to ensure the production process and available raw materials are always maintained.

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

This paper tries to analyze the data on natural disasters in Jambi Province to predict the disasters that will occur in the following year. The historical disaster data is used as processed data and training data to estimate the number of disaster events and types of disasters that may occur. Based on the results of research and prediction calculations with probability values in the Markov Chains method on the percentage value of the probability of natural disasters in Jambi Province. In comparison, the possibility of flooding is very high compared to the probability of landslides, cyclones, and forest and land fires which is 62%. The lowest probability of disaster is landslides which are 20%. The probability of occurrence is 38% for tornadoes, and land and forest fire incidence is 30%. From the Markov chain analysis, it is obtained the probability value of a disaster from each disaster next periods until it reaches a stable, a fixed value, balance or equilibrium, namely for floods and landslides in the 8th period, namely August 2021, for Tornado events in the 8th period. 4 which is April 2021 and for forest and land fires in the 16th period, namely April 2023.

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